

What Makes Wind Energy Annoying to Locals?

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empirical question

- defining annoyance
- proportion of annoyed locals
- consequences

annoyance – evaluation of a perception

- single item assessment, „not annoyed – very annoyed“
- comparable to an attitude assessment, „do not like – like very much“
- assess a general evaluation of the wind turbine impact
- captures no information on the stress reactions

average annoyance induced by wind turbines rather low

Shadow-flicker and noise limited to those experiencing it on their property.

„Strongly” Annoyed Stress Scale (Inclusive Symptoms)

Residents represent a small portion of the population.

few differences between U.S. and European annoyance stress levels

% (n) total n	U.S. National Survey	European Sample
sound	1.1 % (16) 1441	4.3 % (28) 657
landscape change	1.5 % (22) 1441	0.0 % (0) 445
lighting	1.2 % (18) 1441	1.2 % (10) 817
shadow flicker	0.2 % (3) 1441	0.2 % (1) 445
total	2.3 % (33) 1441	3.7 % (38) 1029

high levels of acceptance on local level – constant result pattern

Example: U.S. National Survey (Firestone et al., 2018)

social dimensions of the most important annoyance factors

**participation is crucial –
besides most possible emission reduction and political support**

- participation on eye sight
with a legitimate composition of participants
- communication skills and methods need practice
- empower locals by using neutral intermediaries
- disentangle annoyance and stress impact
- show the broader picture – energy system transformation

vision: locals as hosts – planners and operators as guests

selection of literature

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